

Metadata for the list of alien species in the Prince Edward Islands

This is the metadata for the Prince Edward Islands' species list as part of the report "The status of biological invasions and their management in South Africa". For the last published report see <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3947613> for general details see <http://iasreport.sanbi.org.za>

The species list itself will be in the general file name of "NSRBISA_PEs_Species_list_YYYYMMDD.xlsx". The file is stored as an Excel spreadsheet. This is in part as that format includes italics (in particular for scientificName), and also so it is more easily accessible for users of the report.

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For a full description of the indicators used in the report and for some of the coding of the confidence levels used below see: Wilson et al. (2018) Indicators for monitoring biological invasions at a national level. *Journal of Applied Ecology*, 55, 2612–2620. doi: 10.1111/1365-2664.13251; noting that the details in this document take precedence over those in the paper.

Documents that explain the Darwin core fields used are available at: <http://rs.gbif.org/> & <https://dwc.tdwg.org/terms/>

If there are multiple values in any field, these are separated by a pipe-delimiter '|' with no spaces (e.g., releaseInNature|escapeFromConfinement). If there are multiple values in a field and want to select only some of them can use "=FIND("KZN";[@RangeBroad])" and then sort or filter the dataset by this new column.

The value NA [which means not available (as per R)] is used either:

- where there is no information in a cell;
- there is some uncertainty as to whether effort has been made to find the value;
- information has been looked for and not found; or
- there is no applicable value for that cell.

The interpretation of NA should be given in the specific field in this document.

In some cases, NE is used to mean Not Evaluated (e.g., in IUCN assessments like the Red List and EICAT). This can be because either the status report team has not evaluated it or that nobody has.

These metadata are only for the Prince Edward Islands (two sub-Antarctic islands that are part of South Africa), there are similar but discrete metadata and species lists for continental South Africa, see <https://zenodo.org/record/8047672> and go to the latest version.

Details of how the species list is produced are presented in a workflow that accompanies the report (go to <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8047682> and access the latest version). The process of updating the species list involves the creation of interim files. In some cases on the interim files, the fields 'isNative' or 'occurrenceStatus' are scored as 'check'. Until these issues are resolved the taxon will not be incorporated into the species list. The interim files are available on request.

REFERENCING AND BIBLIOGRAPHY

The species list includes a bibliography as a separate tab on the .xlsx file using the reference style of PenSoft <https://neobiota.pensoft.net/about#CitationsandReferences>.

In the species list itself sources are cited: one author Winzer (2023); two authors: Zengeya and Faulkner (2001), Three or more authors: Miza et al. (1998). When more than one source is cited they are separated by pipe-delimiters separating values.

For a web-site or database: 'BODATSA (12 April 2023)'; or 'GBIF.org (12 April 2023)'. A specific data download can be written in full in the source column 'GBIF.org (24 January 2022) <https://doi.org/10.15468/dl.5fswvr>', though this is not essential. In all cases there should be a generic reference to the source in the bibliography. By contrast a generic web-site column would be written as: 'The Barcode of Life Data System (12 April 2023)', with the details and link in the bibliography: 'The Barcode of Life Data System v4 (2023). <https://www.boldsystems.org/>'. Potentially a note can be made as to how the database was searched "A search was done using the search term: 'Prince Edward Islands "Genus species' on the web-site https://www.boldsystems.org/index.php/Public_BINSearch?searchtype=records"

The bibliography for the species list is available on one of the worksheets of the species list.

REFERENCE FOR THIS DOCUMENT

SANBI and CIB XXXX. Metadata for the list of alien species in the Prince Edward Islands. Part of the report series 'The Status of Biological Invasions and their Management in South Africa'. South African National Biodiversity Institute, Kirstenbosch and DSI-NRF Centre of Excellence for Invasion Biology, Stellenbosch.

The doi will depend on the version, for the first version of the metadata see: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7433113> and scroll to the latest version.

REFERENCE FOR THE SPECIES LIST

SANBI and CIB XXXX. List of alien species in the Prince Edward Islands. Part of the report series 'The Status of Biological Invasions and their Management in South Africa'. South African National Biodiversity Institute, Kirstenbosch and DSI-NRF Centre of Excellence for Invasion Biology, Stellenbosch.

The doi will depend on the version, for the first version see: <https://zenodo.org/record/3582016> and scroll to the latest version.

REFERENCES USED IN THIS DOCUMENT

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Blackburn TM, Essl F, Evans T, Hulme PE, Jeschke JM, Kühn I, Kumschick S, Marková Z, Mrugała A, Nentwig W, Pergl J, Pyšek P, Rabitsch W, Ricciardi A, Richardson DM, Sendek A, Vilá M, Wilson JR, Winter M, Genovesi P, Bacher S (2014) A unified classification of alien species based on the magnitude of their environmental impacts. *PLoS Biology* 12: e1001850, doi:10.1371/journal.pbio.1001850. doi:10.1371/journal.pbio.1001850

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scientificName

Question addressed: What is the valid scientific name of the taxon?

Description: The binomial name of the taxon (normally at species level) including the authority as per dwc:scientificName. The choice of whether to include details of subspecific or supraspecific entities is due to data availability and in some cases regulatory listings.

Darwin Core: dwc:scientificName

Type: Character or NA in cases where there is a taxon that is required to be included in the report (e.g., as it is regulated) but that does not have a valid scientificName. In cases where a whole taxon is referred to (e.g., a whole genus) then it should be written as 'Genus Authority'

taxonRank

Question addressed: The taxonomic rank of the most specific name in the scientificName.

Description: This provides information as to the level of identification given in the scientificName

Darwin Core: dwc:taxonRank

Type: Factor with eight or more levels, note can be higher level than genus

Value	Definition
fam.	Family
gen.	Genus
sect.	Section (between genus and subspecies)
gx.	Grex (used for flocks of orchids)
complex	Species complex
sp.	Species (will be for most taxa)
subsp.	Sub-species
cv.	Cultivar
f.	Forma (form)
var.	Varietas (variety)
biotype	Biotype
strain	Strain

scientificNameSource

Description: The taxonomic backbone used for the scientificName. An 'accessed date' should be provided if the information came from a database, and a web-link as appropriate. Note that the full reference will be included in the bibliography. See the section "REFERENCING AND BIBLIOGRAPHY" at the start of this document for more details

Type: Factor, number of levels will vary over time

Values: This is a list of sources used for nomenclature. In general for plants the backbone used is BODATSA. For all non-plant taxa the backbone used is the Global Biodiversity Information Facility). However, for many taxa these are not sufficient, in particular BODATSA only includes names of alien plant species found outside of captivity or cultivation and there are often delays between a change

in nomenclature and an update processed in GBIF (if such updates are fed through). Value of NA is possible for example for regulated species that are not valid taxa, or for hybrids.

Value	Scope	Description and link
BODATSA	Native plants Alien plants found outside of captivity or cultivation	The botanical database of Southern Africa, http://posa.sanbi.org/ . Annual updates published as the South African National Plant Checklist.
GBIF.org	All taxa (not to be used for plant taxa in this database)	Global Biodiversity Information Facility, https://www.gbif.org/ . GBIF in turn uses various other primary sources for nomenclature, but the goal is not to list these here.
ICTV	Viruses	International Committee on Taxonomy of Viruses, https://ictv.global/ .
POWO	All plants. To be used primarily for taxa not found in BODATSA. Conflicts between BODATSA and POWO are to be resolved on a case by case basis	Plants of the World Online, https://powo.science.kew.org/ .
IPNI	All plants, should feed through to POWO and BODATSA but there can be delays	The International Plant Name Index (IPNI), https://www.ipni.org/ .
name_not_resolved	All taxa	There is on-going confusion around the name, e.g., a species complex or similar that has not been resolved.
Nemaplex	Nematodes not found in GBIF	THE "NEMATODE-PLANT EXPERT INFORMATION SYSTEM" A Virtual Encyclopedia on Soil and Plant Nematodes. http://nemaplex.ucdavis.edu/ http://nemaplex.ucdavis.edu/Uppermnus/genspecsearch.htm .
WoRMS	Marine taxa not found in GBIF	The World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) aims to provide an authoritative and comprehensive list of names of marine organisms, including information on synonymy. https://www.marinespecies.org/ .
Zachariades_2021_African_Entomology	Biological control agents released on plants, names not currently in GBIF	https://doi.org/10.4001/003.029.1077 .

Example:

BODATSA (12 April 2023)|POWO (12 April 2023)

or if a link is included,

BODATSA (12 April 2023) <http://posa.sanbi.org/sanbi/record/details/6526ca7f-a2d5-4a47-ac09-f72dc5194838>|POWO (12 April 2023)
<https://powo.science.kew.org/taxon/urn:lsid:ipni.org:names:469663-1>

otherNamesUsed

Description: Synonyms, names misapplied, or names for which there were typos or no authority provided in the original source. These might have appeared in the regulations or in one of the data sources used. The names in this column have been incorporated into scientificName based on the scientificNameSource used. It is not intended to be a complete list of synonyms for a particular taxon but is a pragmatic list so that people can search for taxa that they might think are otherwise missing. Information on what was done is available in the intermediate data file for a particular source (see the workflow).

Type: Character or NA, can be several values separated by a pipe delimiter. The full names including authorities should be added, including cases where there were typos.

kingdom

Description: The full scientific name of the kingdom in which the taxon is classified. The values are as per GBIF. Incertae sedis is Latin for 'of uncertain placement'.

Darwin Core: dwc:kingdom

Type: Factor

Values: Animalia, Archaea, Bacteria, Chromista, Fungi, Plantae, Protozoa, Viruses , incertae sedis

Note: the values given here (and for phylum, class, order, and family) should not be regarded as authoritative as they are not automatically updated. The values are merely presented for user convenience. If these are to be used for any practical purpose, please refer back to the appropriate taxonomic backbone. The values presented were taken from GBIF, but the date on which this happened is not captured.

phylum

Description: The full scientific name of the phylum or division in which the taxon is classified.

Darwin Core: dwc:phylum

Type: Factor, NA is not a possible value

Values: (examples) Chordata (phylum). Bryophyta (division).

Note: see note under kingdom

class

Description: The full scientific name of the class in which the taxon is classified.

Darwin Core: dwc:class

Type: Factor, NA is a possible value

Values: (examples) Mammalia, Hepaticopsida

Note: see note under kingdom

order

Description: The full scientific name of the order in which the taxon is classified, the order level classification should be as per POWO for plants or as per GBIF.

Darwin Core: dwc:order

Type: Character

Note: see note under kingdom

family

Description: The full scientific name of the family in which the taxon is classified, the family level classification should be as per POWO for plants or as per GBIF.

Darwin Core: dwc:family

Type: Character

Note: see note under kingdom

vernacularName

Question addressed: What is the taxon commonly known as in the Prince Edward Islands?

Description: This is intended to be the predominant common name used to describe the taxon in the Prince Edward Islands. The common name used is generally the English common name, recognising that more than one English common name may exist, and that common names in other South African official languages also exist. Exceptions are made when a non-English common name is predominantly or exclusively used to describe a species (e.g., in the case of *Acacia cyclops*, the common name “rooikrans” is used in preference to the English “red eye”).

Darwin Core: dwc:vernacularName

Type: character, or NA if no common name was found in usage. Lower case should be used throughout except for proper nouns.

RegulatoryListing

Question addressed: Is the taxon regulated as an alien species under South African law?

Description: The listing as per the NEM:BA A&IS Regulations of 2020. Ref: Department of Environment, Forestry and Fisheries (2020) National Environmental Management: Biodiversity Act, 2004 (Act no. 10 of 2004): Alien and Invasive Species Lists. Government Gazette, Pretoria, 31–77 pp.

Note: the exact wording of the listing might be different from the scientificName (e.g., *Acacia decurrens* Willd. Is listed as ‘*Acacia decurrens* Willd. And hybrids, varieties and selections’); context-specific only refers to variation in the listing specified in the ‘categories’ field (e.g., in the regulations *A. decurrens* is listed in the category field only as “2”, but in the exemptions field it is listed as “Exempted for an existing plantation”, this is not regarded as context-specific here). In the 2014 and 2016 lists certain taxa were listed as prohibited (i.e. they were not present in the country and were not allowed to be introduced), however this prohibited list has since been removed.

If a taxon is not present in the country it is (or should be) regarded as unlisted, unless there is a discrepancy in the regulatory lists.

If the taxon is only described at a higher level than that at which the taxon is regulated then it is scored as uncertain. For example, there is a record of a dermestid from the Prince Edward Islands but only *Trogoderma granarium* is listed.

Darwin Core: see extension <http://rs.gbif.org/vocabulary/gisin/2.0/regulatory.xml> but the allowed vocabulary is specific to South Africa.

Relevant indicator(s): 4.1, 4.2–4.9

Type: Factor with 9 levels

Value	Definition
1a	
1b	
2	
3	
Context-specific	Taxa that are listed in different categories depending on the area or ecosystem in which they are found and/or for which there are specific exemptions and/or prohibitions.
Not.listed	Taxa that are not listed under the version of the NEM:BA A&IS Lists as specified above. It can be assumed that they were never previously listed or formally proposed for listing (see categories below).
Not.listed:was.listed	Taxa that have in the past been listed, but are not currently listed.
Not.listed:was.proposed	Taxa that have in the past been formally proposed for listing (i.e., in a list published in the government gazette), but that were never formally listed.
Uncertain	The taxon might be listed, but the identity of the taxon is at a higher level than the regulatory listing, i.e., it is not clear whether the taxon is actually listed or not.

regulatoryGrouping

Description: In the NEM:BA A&IS Lists (2014, 2016, and 2020) taxa are listed in high-level groupings that correspond to a mix of taxonomic groupings and where the taxa occur. These groupings are included for reference only for taxa that are listed. In a few cases this grouping does not correspond to the kingdom (e.g., some marine algae are listed as marine plants).

Type: Factor with 12 levels (as well as NA for taxa which are not currently listed as per RegulatoryListing)

Value	Definition
Amphibian	

Value	Definition
Bird	
Fish.FW	Freshwater fish
Fish.M	Marine fish (there are no alien marine fish recorded from South African waters, but there was one prohibited species in the 2014 and 2016 lists).
Invert.FW	Freshwater invertebrates
Invert.M	Marine invertebrates
Invert.T	Terrestrial invertebrates
Mammal	
Microbe	Microbial species (including all fungi)
Plant.M	Marine plants
Plant.FWT	Terrestrial and freshwater plants
Reptile	

isNative

Question addressed: Is the taxon native to one or both of the Prince Edward Islands?

Description: If a taxon is native to at least one of the Prince Edward Islands (i.e. TRUE), then the taxon does not belong in this dataset unless:

- at some point it was present as an alien species elsewhere in the Prince Edward Islands (occurrenceStatus=present); or
- the taxon is (or was) prohibited from being introduced to another part of the Prince Edward Islands under regulations; or
- a risk analysis (/assessment) has been conducted on the taxon; or
- the taxon was at some point classified as alien to one or both of the Prince Edward Islands although the taxon's nativity has since been settled and it is clear it is native.

isNative does not align with the Darwin Core variable dwc:establishmentMeans, as terms like introduced confound whether it is alien to a region with dwc:degreeOfEstablishment or the field IntroductionStatus coded here (cf. Groom et al. 2019). For a discussion on the criteria used to classify something as cryptogenic see Essl et al. (2018), with terms as per Carlton (1996) and Richardson et al. (2011). The category of not evaluated as proposed by Essl et al. (2018) is not used here, as if there has been no evaluation of a species' nativity then it also does not belong to this dataset. The category of data deficient as proposed by Essl et al. (2018) is also not used here, and rather all taxa where nativity is highly uncertain are classed as cryptogenic.

Type: Factor with 4 levels.

Value	Definition
Cryptogenic	Those of unknown biogeographic origin, which cannot be definitively categorised as native to any part of the Prince Edward Islands, but neither can be definitively categorised as alien to the Prince Edward Islands where it is present.
FALSE	
TRUE	
DD	An assessment of biogeographic status is unfeasible (data deficient) because of uncertainty in the taxon identity.

Note: There is no valid use of NA, as if nativity has not been evaluated, the taxon should not be included in the data-set. The taxon might be included in an interim data-set in which case the value will be set to 'check', the check must happen before the taxon is incorporated into the actual list.

isNativeConfidence

Description: The level of confidence in the scoring of isNative

Type: Factor with 2 levels (and NA if isNative is NA; and NA if isNative is Cryptogenic). A third level is listed in Wilson et al. 2018, but if the nativity in dispute, and confidence is lower than 90% that it is native to somewhere OR lower than 90% that it is alien everywhere it is, then it should be classed as Cryptogenic.

Value	Definition
high	All databases (at least one of which is authoritative) state that the taxon is native (or alien) and there is no evidence of debate about nativity.
medium	Categorised as native (or alien) in the most authoritative sources although some references report the opposite with no detailed published analysis confirming nativity. OR the only sources in which nativity is recorded are not authoritative.

isNativeSource

Description: The reference or sources that were used to score isNative

Type: character or NA

Values: see REFERENCING AND BIBLIOGRAPHY for details

occurrenceStatus

Question addressed: Does the taxon occur in the Prince Edward Islands (as of December 2022)?

Description: This will include both alien and native ranges, for specification of whether it is present as an alien see introductionStatus or degreeOfEstablishment.

Darwin Core: dwc:occurrenceStatus. Not all the values of the vocabulary are used (common, irregular, rare) as information on abundance is stored under organismQuantity.

Relevant indicator: 2.1

Type: Factor with 4 levels

Values: Can inherit presences from introductionStatus and degreeOfEstablishment, but can only inherit absences if used in combination with isNative.

Value	Definition
absent	A reasoned analysis of the evidence suggests the taxon is not present in The Prince Edward Islands as of December 2022 OR there is no evidence of presence.
present	There is evidence to document the presence of the taxon in The Prince Edward Islands as of December 2022.
doubtful	There is some evidence of the taxon having been present in The Prince Edward Islands, but there is doubt over the evidence or whether it is still present as of December 2022, including taxonomic or geographic imprecision in the records.
NE	There has been no specific attempt to ascertain if the taxon is in (or has been in) The Prince Edward Islands.

occurrenceStatusConfidence

Description: The level of confidence in the scoring of occurrenceStatus

Type: Factor with 2 levels (and NA if occurrenceStatus is Doubtful or NotEvaluated). A third level is listed in Wilson et al. 2018, but if the species has been recorded as present but the record is either questioned or last record from a substantial time ago, then occurrenceStatus should be classed as 'doubtful' and confidence as NA.

Value	Definition
high	For presence: physical sample lodged in a recognised collection identified by an expert OR molecular confirmation of a sample collected in the last 50 years AND field notes in the past decade confirming presence.
	For absence: there is no evidence the taxon is in The Prince Edward Islands despite surveys in relevant areas by individuals with field experience of identifying the taxon, with appropriate sampling AND there are no putative pathways by which it could have recently been introduced OR there is documented evidence declaring eradication / loss of the population, there are no likely putative pathways for recent reintroductions, and it has not been seen for over a decade despite resurveys OR there is a reasoned analysis (e.g., an argument map) that comes to a strong conclusion.
medium	For presence: no physical sample or molecular confirmation, or sample collected over a decade ago with no field confirmations in past ten years.
	For absence: there is no evidence the taxon is in The Prince Edward Islands in the relevant sources OR there is documented evidence declaring eradication / loss of the populations OR there is a reasoned analysis (e.g., an argument map) that comes to a weak conclusion.

occurrenceStatusSource

Description: The reference or source used to score occurrenceStatus, this should include notes on whether there is a physical specimen and a source; whether there is molecular confirmation that the specimen is that species and provide the source; whether there is a literature record of presence of the specimen and provide source; and whether there has been recent field confirmation and again provide source. In each case, the answers are yes, no, unclear (e.g., molecular results might indicate several potential taxa or a field evaluation might only be to a genus level), or NE (i.e., not evaluated, there has been no attempt to look to see if such data have been collected or not).

Type: Structured text field

Values: "NE" if occurrenceStatus is NotEvaluated OR

"Physical specimen (yes/no/NE) ref|Molecular confirmation (yes/no/unclear/NE) ref|Literature reference (yes/no/unclear/NE) ref|Field evaluation (yes/no/unclear/NE) ref"

Example: 'Physical specimen (NE)|Molecular confirmation (NE)|Literature reference (yes) Zachariades (2021)|Field observation (yes) Zachariades (2021)'

degreeOfEstablishment

Question addressed: To what degree is the taxon where it is alien in the Prince Edward Islands surviving, reproducing, and has expanded its range (as of December 2022)?

Description: The coding is taken from the Unified Framework for Biological Invasions (Blackburn et al. 2011) with the wording and description based largely on the Darwin Core term (dwc:degreeOfEstablishment; (Groom et al. 2019)), with the use of native rather than indigenous and the separation of A into A0 and A1 to indicate cases where things have disappeared from the Prince Edward Islands. In cases where it is clear that a taxon can be categorised at a certain level, but

it is not clear if it can be categorised at a higher level (e.g., it has certainly naturalised C3, but there isn't clear spread D1, or that the spread results in new self-sustaining populations D2, then it should be scored as C3).

Relevant indicator(s): 2.1.3

Type: Factor with 12 levels (as well as NA):

Value	Definition
A0	Never introduced beyond limits of native range to [a part of] The Prince Edward Islands.
A1	Has been introduced beyond limits of native range to The Prince Edward Islands, but no longer present.
B1	Individuals transported beyond limits of native range, and in captivity or quarantine (i.e. individuals provided with conditions suitable for them, but explicit measures of containment are in place).
B2	Individuals transported beyond limits of native range, and in cultivation (i.e. individuals provided with conditions suitable for them but explicit measures to prevent dispersal are limited at best).
B3	Individuals transported beyond limits of native range, and directly released into novel environment.
C0	Individuals released outside of captivity or cultivation in location where introduced, but incapable of surviving for a significant period.
C1	Individuals surviving outside of captivity or cultivation in location where introduced, no reproduction.
C2	Individuals surviving outside of captivity or cultivation in location where introduced, reproduction occurring, but population not self-sustaining.
C3	Individuals surviving outside of captivity or cultivation in location where introduced, reproduction occurring, and population self-sustaining.
D1	Self-sustaining population outside of captivity or cultivation, with individuals surviving a significant distance from the original point of introduction.
D2	Self-sustaining population outside of captivity or cultivation, with individuals surviving and reproducing a significant distance from the original point of introduction.
E	Fully invasive species, with individuals dispersing, surviving and reproducing at multiple sites across a greater or lesser spectrum of habitats and extent of occurrence.

degreeOfEstablishmentConfidence

Description: The level of confidence in the scoring of degreeOfEstablishment

Type: Factor with 3 levels (and NA if degreeOfEstablishment is NA)

Value	Definition
high	A0–A1: use the criteria for defining absence (occurrenceStatusConfidence) checking against evidence for historical presence (occurrenceStatusConfidence) to separate the two categories.
	B1–D2: based on recent (within the last decade) published field observations specifically using the coding of degreeOfEstablishment.
	E: based on published field observations specifically using the coding of degreeOfEstablishment (regardless of date, as taxa are very unlikely to move from back to D2 or earlier, even despite significant population crashes).
medium	A0–A1: use the criteria for defining absence (occurrenceStatusConfidence) checking against evidence for historical presence (occurrenceStatusConfidence) to separate the two categories.

Value	Definition
	B1–E: based on historical (older than the last decade) published field observations with enough detailed information (and demonstrable survey effort) to code them according to degreeOfEstablishment.
low	A0–A1: use the criteria for defining absence (occurrenceStatus AND occurrenceStatusConfidence).
	B1–E: interpreted from distribution data in an atlas project or similar listing project (specify interpretation made in the source, if it is not clear what the survey effort was or if the taxon is correctly identified do not score degreeOfEstablishment).

degreeOfEstablishmentSource

Description: The reference or sources that were used to score degreeOfEstablishment

Type: Structured text field

Values: Field evaluation using Unified Framework (yes/no), if 'yes' provide a reference, and details of survey method / effort; if 'no' provide distribution dataset that was used and how it was interpreted.

IntroductionStatus

Question addressed: A more basic answer to the question addressed by degreeOfEstablishment: To what degree is the taxon where it is alien in the Prince Edward Islands surviving, reproducing, and has expanded its range (as of December 2022)? This also specifically flags taxa with native-alien populations (sensu Nelufule et al. 2022).

Description: Aligns with high-level introduction status as per the first report. Not part of Darwin Core.

Relevant indicator(s): 2.1.2

Type: Factor with 3 major categories, and 2 sub-categories, as well as NA. Note: can be inherited from degreeOfEstablishment as below:

Value	Definition
NA	If degreeOfEstablishment is A0 or A1 OR if occurrenceStatus is absent or doubtful OR if isNative is TRUE and occurrenceStatus is present, there is no indication of any individuals in what would be considered an alien range OR if it is not evaluated.
presentAsAlienNotNaturalised	B1–C2, includes a range of species from those in quarantine to those that are reproducing outside of captivity or cultivation but where there is no clear evidence of having formed self-sustaining populations.
NaturalisedNotInvasive	C3–D1, species where there is naturalisation, and possibly spread, but there is no clear evidence of forming self-sustaining populations at a significant distance from point of introduction.

Value	Definition
NaturalisedNotInvasive:NativeAlienPopulations	The subcategory NativeAlienPopulations is used in cases where a taxon is native to a part of The Prince Edward Islands but has formed naturalised populations in another part of The Prince Edward Islands to which the taxon is alien.
Invasive	D2–E, populations are self-sustaining a significant distance from the point of introduction.
Invasive:NativeAlienPopulations	The subcategory NativeAlienPopulations is used in cases where a taxon is native to a part of The Prince Edward Islands but has formed invasive populations in another part of The Prince Edward Islands to which the taxon is alien.

IntroductionStatusConfidence

Description: The level of confidence in the scoring of IntroductionStatus

Type: Factor with 3 levels (and NA if IntroductionStatus is NA)

Value	Definition
high	Inherited from degreeOfEstablishmentConfidence OR based on recent (within last decade) published field observations.
medium	Inherited from degreeOfEstablishmentConfidence OR based on published field observations older than a decade.
low	Inherited from degreeOfEstablishmentConfidence OR based on expert opinion only with no clear indication of last field observation.

IntroductionStatusSource

Description: The reference or sources that were used to score IntroductionStatus

Type: Text (and NA if IntroductionStatus is NA)

Values: Either "see degreeOfEstablishmentSource" or provide ref to field observation / expert opinion

pathway

Question addressed: How did (/does) the taxon arrive in its alien range in the Prince Edward Islands?

Description: The field is based on the broad categories which were initially developed by Hulme et al. (2008), with sub-categories adopted by the CBD (Scalera et al. 2016) and later revised (Harrower et al. 2018). For guidance of their application see Harrower et al. (2018). This coding is currently only available through the Invasive Species Pathways extension to Darwin Core (<http://rs.gbif.org/sandbox/extension/issg-pathway.xml>; Pagad et al. 2015).

Relevant indicator(s): 1.2

Type: Factor with 7 major categories, and 44 sub-categories. Nesting is indicated by a colon and multiple levels that apply are separated by a pipe delimiter. For example:
 releaseInNature:hunting|releaseInNature:landscapeImprovement

Values:

Value
releaseInNature
releaseInNature:biologicalControl
releaseInNature:erosionControl
releaseInNature:fisheryInTheWild
releaseInNature:hunting
releaseInNature:landscapImprovement
releaseInNature:conservationOrWildlifeManagement
releaseInNature:releasedForUse
releaseInNature:otherIntentionalRelease
escapeFromConfinement
escapeFromConfinement:agriculture
escapeFromConfinement:aquacultureMariculture
escapeFromConfinement:publicGardenZooAquaria
escapeFromConfinement:pet
escapeFromConfinement:farmedAnimals
escapeFromConfinement:forestry
escapeFromConfinement:fur
escapeFromConfinement:horticulture
escapeFromConfinement:ornamentalNonHorticulture
escapeFromConfinement:research
escapeFromConfinement:liveFoodLiveBait
escapeFromConfinement:otherEscape
transportContaminant
transportContaminant:contaminantNursery
transportContaminant:contaminateBait
transportContaminant:foodContaminant
transportContaminant:contaminantOnAnimals
transportContaminant:parasitesOnAnimals
transportContaminant:contaminantOnPlants
transportContaminant:parasitesOnPlants
transportContaminant:seedContaminant
transportContaminant:timberTrade
transportContaminant:transportationHabitatMaterial
transportStowaway
transportStowaway:fishingEquipment
transportStowaway:containerBulk
transportStowaway:hitchhikersAirplane
transportStowaway:hitchhikersShip
transportStowaway:machineryEquipment
transportStowaway:people
transportStowaway:packingMaterial
transportStowaway:ballastWater
transportStowaway:hullFouling
transportStowaway:vehicles
transportStowaway:otherTransport
corridor
corridor:waterwaysBasinsSeas

Value
corridor:tunnelsBridges
unaided
unaided:naturalDispersal
unknown

pathwayConfidence

Description: The confidence with which the variable pathway was scored for a given taxon

Type: Factor with 3 levels (and NA if pathway is Unknown)

Value	Definition
high	Direct evidence that it was introduced along a pathway.
medium	Indirect evidence (e.g., correlation between pathway and sites in the country).
low	Inferred based on species traits and/or other regions.

pathwaySource

Description: The reference or sources that were used to score the pathway for a given taxon

Type: text

Values: reference(s)

eventDateIntroduction

Question addressed: When was the taxon first introduced as an alien to the Prince Edward Islands?

Description: The year in which the taxon was first introduced to the Prince Edward Islands (i.e. dwc:eventDate).

In some definitions introduction is taken to be the first record outside of captivity or cultivation (cf. IPBES IAS Assessment), however here we take the literal approach, i.e., the date when a taxon is first introduced to the islands from overseas. Introductions thus include taxa which could potentially be brought into quarantine (and might never be released). Additional eventDates might be added in future that are closer to the sense in which IPBES has used the term (e.g., date of first record of naturalisation). Should conform to ISO 8601:2004(E), the standard does allow for date ranges. This is not, necessarily, the same as the date of first record, though obviously the date of first record provides an important estimate for this.

Relevant indicator(s): 1.2, 2.1

Type: An ordered factor with potential levels up to 31 December 2022.

Values: Any dates before the current era (i.e. BC) are marked as negative.

eventDateIntroductionConfidence

Description: The confidence with which the variable eventDateIntroduction was scored for a given taxon. There are two aspects that determine this confidence level. First the degree of confidence that the first record was a real record, and second how close to the date of introduction was the first record.

Type: Factor with 3 levels (and NA if eventDateIntroduction is NA)

Value	Definition
high	There is reliable evidence both that the taxon was recorded in that year (e.g., from herbarium records or DNA samples) AND that the taxon was not introduced earlier. This could include records of deliberate introductions of organisms that would not otherwise arrive accidentally. The estimate is highly likely to be within 2 years of the actual date of introduction.
medium	There is strong evidence that a taxon was recorded that year / date range, but there could have been earlier records. OR The evidence that the taxon was recorded that year / date range is weak, but it is unlikely that there could have been earlier records. OR The site of first detection is associated with a likely introduction pathway that can be assigned to a particular date range. The estimate is highly likely to be within 20 years of the actual date.
low	The first record of the taxon is disputed and only much more recently do reliable records confirm presence. OR It is highly possible that introductions were occurring but the taxon was not detected as there was no explicit search efforts in place. The estimate is likely to be decades from the actual date.

Note: Importantly there are a few caveats to this value. First when a taxon was first introduced to the Prince Edward Islands might be much earlier than date of the introduction that subsequently led to an established and/or invasive population (many introductions fail). Second, the first record depends on the search effort, this is not explicitly measured here but could potentially be. For example, if a pest was not previously intercepted at the border despite border inspections being in place, but shortly after the first interceptions were recorded the pest was found to have established in the field, it could be assumed that border inspections would have picked up introductions. The first interception therefore provides evidence that introductions were occurring, there is evidence that the taxon was detectable, and the search in this case was probably appropriate, though of course the exact date of introduction that led to the establishment is not known.

eventDateIntroductionSource

Description: The reference or sources that were used to score the eventDateIntroduction for a given taxon

Type: text

Values: reference(s)

RangeBroadAdmin

Question addressed: How widespread is the alien taxon outside of captivity/cultivation in the Prince Edward Islands —in terms of broad administrative regions?

Description: This lists the occupancy of specific administrative regions, which in the case of the PEIs it refers to the two separate islands, Marion (MI) and Prince Edward (PEI), and their terrestrial and freshwater administrative regions, plus the marine.

Relevant indicator(s): 2.2.1

Type: A factor with 3 levels (and NA if there is no range OR if the range is not known with this level of precision).

Values: Multiple levels that apply are separated by a pipe delimiter.

Value	Definition
MI.FWT	Marion Island terrestrial and freshwater (although currently no freshwater invasions have been recorded, Greve et al. 2020).
PEI.FWT	Prince Edward Island terrestrial and freshwater (although currently no freshwater invasions have been recorded, Greve et al. 2020).
PEIs.M	Prince Edward Islands marine ecoregion (although currently no marine invasions have been recorded, Greve et al. 2020)

RangeBroadAdminConfidence

Description: The confidence with which the variable RangeBroadAdmin was scored for a given taxon

Type: Factor with 3 levels (and NA if RangeBroadAdmin is NA)

Value	Definition
high	Included in a formal verified atlas or mapping project based on recent surveys with adequate ground-truthing. There is some indication that there have been surveys at sites where the taxon is not recorded as present.
medium	Data from an atlas project, though it is not explicit that sites where it is not recorded as present would have been recorded/some sites might not have been surveyed.
low	Interpreted from expert opinion.

RangeBroadAdminSource

Description: The reference or sources that were used to score the RangeBroadAdmin for a given taxon

Type: character or NA

Values: reference(s)

RangeBroadEcol

Question addressed: How widespread is the alien taxon outside of captivity/cultivation in the Prince Edward Islands—in terms of broad ecological regions?

Description: This lists the occupancy of specific biogeographic regions (the biomes for terrestrial systems following Mucina and Rutherford (2008); and one marine ecoregion, noting that there are no separate freshwater ecoregions on the PEIs, and that this section excludes the continental South Africa ecoregions).

Relevant indicator(s): 2.2.1

Type: A factor with 3 levels (and NA if there is no range OR if the range is not known with this level of precision). Multiple levels that apply are separated by a pipe delimiter.

Values: if a factor with several levels as a table (e.g., for confidence levels)

Value	Definition
PD	Terrestrial ecoregion - Polar desert
ST	Terrestrial ecoregion - Subantarctic Tundra
PEI.M	Marine ecoregion - Prince Edward Island (although currently no marine invasions have been recorded, Greve et al. 2020).

RangeBroadEcolConfidence

Description: The confidence with which the variable RangeBroadEcol was scored for a given taxon

Type: Factor with 3 levels (and NA if RangeBroadEcol is NA)

Value	Definition
high	Included in a formal verified atlas or mapping project based on recent surveys with adequate ground-truthing. There is some indication that there have been surveys at sites where the taxon is not recorded as present.
medium	Data from an atlas project, though it is not explicit that sites where it is not recorded as present would have been recorded/some sites might not have been surveyed.
low	Interpreted from expert opinion.

RangeBroadEcolSource

Description: The reference or sources that were used to score the RangeBroadEcol for a given taxon

Type: character or NA

Values: reference(s)

RangeHMGC

Question addressed: How widespread is the alien taxon outside of captivity/cultivation in the Prince Edward Islands—in terms of half-minute grid cells?

Description: The number of half-minute grid cells occupied by the taxon in its alien range as per le Roux et al. (2013) (for where they are found, consult the data sources)

Relevant indicator(s): 2.2.2

Type: integer

Values: numeric 1–557 (being '557' the maximum number of half minute grid cells in the Prince Edward Islands) or NA if there is no range or if not known with this level of precision

RangeHMGCConfidence

Description: The confidence with which the variable RangeHMGC was scored for a given taxon

Type: Factor with 3 levels (and NA if RangeHMGC is NA)

Value	Definition
high	Included in a formal verified atlas or mapping project based on recent surveys with adequate ground-truthing. There is some indication that there have been surveys at sites where the taxon is not recorded as present.
medium	Data from an atlas project, though it is not explicit that sites where it is not recorded as present would have been recorded/some sites might not have been surveyed.
low	Interpreted from expert opinion.

RangeHMGCCSource

Description: The reference or sources that were used to score the RangeHMGC for a given taxon

Type: character or NA

Values: reference(s)

RangeExact

Question addressed: How widespread is the alien taxon outside of captivity/cultivation in the Prince Edward Islands—in terms of area occupied?

Description: An estimate of the area occupied by the species at a specific resolution

Relevant indicator(s): 2.2.3

Type: Numeric or NA if there is no range or if not known with this level of precision

Values: depends on RangeExactType

RangeExactType

Description: The units in which the range is presented (e.g., ha, km of coastline, rivers)

Relevant indicator(s): If none delete

Type: factor

Values: levels to be determined and modified as data added e.g., ha—occupied area in terms of hectares putting a polygon around point patterns of individual discrete populations

RangeExactConfidence

Description: The confidence with which the variable RangeExact was scored for a given taxon

Type: Factor with 3 levels (and NA if RangeExact is NA)

Value	Definition
high	Data based on a project within the last decade specifically designed to map the range of the taxon in question, with search effort explicit and sufficient to determine where taxa are and where they are not. Might include citizen science component for easily identified taxa. Appropriate statistical technique used to estimate total range size (particular if disjunct distributions).
medium	Data from atlas project or general mapping project with indication of sampling effort, but data not complete or not recent (e.g., >10 years old).

Value	Definition
low	No absence data, no clear statistical methodology for estimating range size, or very broad estimate.

RangeExactSource

Description: The reference or sources that were used to score RangeExact for a given taxon

Type: character or NA

Values: reference(s)

RangeFreeText

Question addressed: How widespread is the alien taxon outside of captivity/cultivation in the Prince Edward Islands—text description of current range?

Description: Notes as to the range can be made, e.g., if it is restricted only to specific habitats like urban areas or harbours

Relevant indicator(s): 2.2

Type: character or NA

RangeFreeTextSource

Description: The reference or sources that were used to score RangeFreeText for a given taxon

Type: character or NA

Values: reference(s)

organismQuantityCategorical

Question addressed: How abundant is the taxon in its alien range in the Prince Edward Islands as of December 2022—is there a qualitative measure per spatial unit?

Description: Categorical measure of abundance per species per locality, with localities defined using organismQuantityCategoricalType (cf. dwc:organismQuantity and dwc:organismQuantityType)

Relevant indicator(s): 2.3.1

Type: Factor with 3 levels

Value	Definition
TRUE	An evaluation of abundance based on (absent; rare; occasional; abundant) has been made for the alien taxon at -at least- some of the localities where it occurs.
FALSE	
NA	It is not present.

organismQuantityCategoricalType

Description: the spatial unit(s) for which data on quantities are available

Type: factor

Values: levels to be determined and modified as data added, e.g., provinces, or protected areas

organismQuantityCategoricalConfidence

Description: The confidence with which the variable organismQuantityCategorical was scored for a given taxon

Type: Factor with 3 levels (and NA if organismQuantityCategorical is NA)

Value	Definition
high	Recent survey, technique used well documented, and several people confirming the value obtained (e.g., included in a formal verified atlas or mapping project based on recent surveys with adequate ground-truthing).
medium	Data from an atlas project, or recent survey but only one person.
low	Interpreted from expert opinion, or no clear basis for the value given, or over 10 years ago.

organismQuantityCategoricalSource

Description: The reference or sources that were used to score organismQuantityCategorical for a given taxon

Type: character or NA

Values: reference(s)

organismQuantityExact

Question addressed: How abundant is the taxon in its alien range in the Prince Edward Islands—in terms of an exact overall number?

Description: An estimate of the area occupied by the species at a specific resolution, or numbers of individuals

Relevant indicator(s): 2.3.2

Type: Numeric

organismQuantityExactType

Description: The type of data of organismQuantityExact

Type: Factor with 2 levels (and NA if organismQuantityExact is NA)

Values: if a factor with several levels as a table (e.g., for confidence levels)

Value	Definition
numind	Number of individuals
cca	Condensed canopy area in ha

organismQuantityExactConfidence

Description: The confidence with which the variable organismQuantityExact was scored for a given taxon

Type: Factor with 3 levels (and NA if organismQuantityExact is NA)

Value	Definition
high	Accurate and recent population census, using appropriate statistical techniques.

Value	Definition
medium	Estimation based on sampling that uses assumptions and makes extrapolations.
low	Expert opinion.

organismQuantityExactSource

Description: The reference or sources that were used to score organismQuantityExact for a given taxon

Type: character or NA

Values: reference(s)

organismQuantityDetailed

Question addressed: How abundant is the taxon in its alien range in the Prince Edward Islands—are detailed information available on individuals?

Description: Are detailed data available e.g., on the sizes, ages, or condition of individuals, that make up the population

Relevant indicator(s): 2.3.3

Type: Factor with 2 levels

Values: TRUE or FALSE

organismQuantityDetailedSource

Description: The reference or sources where data on organismQuantity area available

Type: character or NA

Values: reference(s)

impactEICATPrinceEdwardIslands

Question addressed: How severe are the negative environmental impacts of the alien taxon in the Prince Edward Islands?

Description: A single value should be given which is the maximum current recorded environmental impact in the Prince Edward Islands. (Blackburn et al., 2014, Hawkins et al. 2015)

Relevant indicator(s): 2.4

Type: Factor with 7 levels (including NA if there is no alien population and NE if it has not been evaluated within the context of the report)

Value	Definition
MC	Minimal Concern
MN	Minor
MO	Moderate
MR	Major
MV	Massive
DD	Data Deficient
NA	No Alien population

Value	Definition
NE	Not Evaluated

impactEICATPrinceEdwardIslandsConfidence

Description: The confidence with which the variable impactPrinceEdwardIslandsEICAT was scored for a given taxon. Guidance regarding the use of the confidence rating is taken from Hawkins et al. (2015) as modified therein from the EPPO pest risk assessment decision support scheme (Alan MacLeod 09/03/2011; revised 28/04/2011; copied from CAPRA, version 2.74; 2).

Type: Factor with 3 levels (and NA)

Value	Definition
high	Approximately 90% chance of assessment being correct. There is direct relevant observational evidence to support the assessment; and impacts are recorded at the typical spatial scale over which original native communities can be characterised; and there are reliable/good quality data sources on impacts of the taxa; and the interpretation of data/information is straightforward; and data/information are not controversial or contradictory.
medium	There is some direct observational evidence to support the assessment, but some information is inferred; and/or impacts are recorded at a spatial scale which may not be relevant to the scale over which original native communities can be characterized, but extrapolation or downscaling of the data to relevant scales is considered reliable, or to embrace little uncertainty; and/or the interpretation of the data is to some extent ambiguous or contradictory.
low	There is no direct observational evidence to support the assessment, e.g., only inferred data have been used as supporting evidence; and/or impacts are recorded at a spatial scale which is unlikely to be relevant to the scale over which original native communities can be characterized, and extrapolation or downscaling of the data to relevant scales is considered unreliable or to embrace significant uncertainties; and/or evidence is poor and difficult to interpret, e.g., because it is strongly ambiguous; and/or the information sources are considered to be of low quality or contain information that is unreliable.

impactEICATPrinceEdwardIslandsSource

Description: The reference or sources that were used to score impactEICATPrinceEdwardIslands for a given taxon. The reference should be to the impact assessment conducted rather than to all the primary sources.

Type: character or NA

Values: reference(s)

impactEICAT

Question addressed: How severe might the negative environmental impacts of the alien taxon be?

Description: A single value should be given which is the maximum recorded environmental impact in any alien range of the taxon (Blackburn et al. 2014; Hawkins et al. 2015; IUCN 2020). This is included here to give an indication of which taxa are known to cause damage. Note, this does not assess the

likelihood of similar impacts being realised in the Prince Edward Islands (e.g., it does not take into account climatic suitability and environmental context), although information from the Prince Edward Islands might be used in the assessment.

Type: Factor with 7 levels (including NA, note if data aren't available this is NE)

Value	Definition
MC	Minimal Concern
MN	Minor
MO	Moderate
MR	Major
MV	Massive
DD	Data Deficient
NA	No Alien population
NE	Not Evaluated

impactEICATConfidence

Description: The confidence with which the variable impactEICAT was scored for a given taxon.

Guidance regarding the use of the confidence rating is taken from Hawkins et al. (2015) as modified therein from the EPPO pest risk assessment decision support scheme (Alan MacLeod 09/03/2011; revised 28/04/2011; copied from CAPRA, version 2.74; 2).

Type: Factor with 3 levels (and NA)

Value	Definition
high	Approximately 90% chance of assessment being correct. There is direct relevant observational evidence to support the assessment; and impacts are recorded at the typical spatial scale over which original native communities can be characterised; and there are reliable/good quality data sources on impacts of the taxa; and the interpretation of data/information is straightforward; and data/information are not controversial or contradictory.
medium	There is some direct observational evidence to support the assessment, but some information is inferred; and/or impacts are recorded at a spatial scale which may not be relevant to the scale over which original native communities can be characterized, but extrapolation or downscaling of the data to relevant scales is considered reliable, or to embrace little uncertainty; and/or the interpretation of the data is to some extent ambiguous or contradictory.
low	There is no direct observational evidence to support the assessment, e.g., only inferred data have been used as supporting evidence; and/or impacts are recorded at a spatial scale which is unlikely to be relevant to the scale over which original native communities can be characterized, and extrapolation or downscaling of the data to relevant scales is considered unreliable or to embrace significant uncertainties; and/or evidence is poor and difficult to interpret, e.g., because it is strongly ambiguous; and/or the information sources are considered to be of low quality or contain information that is unreliable.

impactEICATSource

Description: The reference or sources that were used to score impactEICAT for a given taxon. The reference should be to the impact assessment conducted rather than to all the primary sources.

Type: character or NA

Values: reference(s), note a single value linked to a published EICAT assessment may be given (rather than all the references in that assessment)

impactSEICATPrinceEdwardIslands

Question addressed: How severe are the negative socio-economic impacts of the alien taxon in the Prince Edward Islands?

Description: A single value should be given which is the maximum recorded socio-economic impact in the Prince Edward Islands (Bacher et al. 2018)

Relevant indicator(s): 2.4

Type: Factor with 7 levels (including NA, note if data aren't available this is NE)

Value	Definition
MC	Minimal Concern
MN	Minor
MO	Moderate
MR	Major
MV	Massive
DD	Data Deficient
NA	No Alien Population
NE	Not Evaluated

impactSEICATPrinceEdwardIslandsConfidence

Description: The confidence with which the variable impactSEICATSouthAfrica was scored for a given taxon. Guidance regarding the use of the confidence rating is taken from Hawkins et al. (2015) as modified therein from the EPPO pest risk assessment decision support scheme (Alan MacLeod 09/03/2011; revised 28/04/2011; copied from CAPRA, version 2.74; 2).

Type: Factor with 3 levels (and NA)

Value	Definition
high	Approximately 90% chance of assessment being correct. There is direct relevant observational evidence to support the assessment; and impacts are recorded at the typical spatial scale over which original native communities can be characterised; and there are reliable/good quality data sources on impacts of the taxa; and the interpretation of data/information is straightforward; and data/information are not controversial or contradictory.

Value	Definition
medium	There is some direct observational evidence to support the assessment, but some information is inferred; and/or impacts are recorded at a spatial scale which may not be relevant to the scale over which original native communities can be characterized, but extrapolation or downscaling of the data to relevant scales is considered reliable, or to embrace little uncertainty; and/or the interpretation of the data is to some extent ambiguous or contradictory.
low	There is no direct observational evidence to support the assessment, e.g., only inferred data have been used as supporting evidence; and/or impacts are recorded at a spatial scale which is unlikely to be relevant to the scale over which original native communities can be characterized, and extrapolation or downscaling of the data to relevant scales is considered unreliable or to embrace significant uncertainties; and/or evidence is poor and difficult to interpret, e.g., because it is strongly ambiguous; and/or the information sources are considered to be of low quality or contain information that is unreliable.

impactSEICATPrinceEdwardIslandsSource

Description: The reference or sources that were used to score impactSEICATPrinceEdwardIslands for a given taxon. The reference should be to the impact assessment conducted rather than to all the primary sources.

Type: character or NA

Values: reference(s), note a single value linked to a published EICAT assessment may be given (rather than all the references in that assessment)

impactSEICAT

Question addressed: How severe might the negative socio-economic impacts of the alien taxon be?

Description: A single value should be given which is the maximum recorded socio-economic impact in any alien range of the taxon (Bacher et al., 2018). This is included here to give an indication of which taxa are known to cause damage elsewhere. This is included here to give an indication of which taxa are known to cause damage. Note, this does not assess the likelihood of similar impacts being realised in the Prince Edward Islands (e.g., it does not take into account climatic suitability and environmental context), although information from the Prince Edward Islands might be used in the assessment.

Type: Factor with 7 levels (including NA, note if data aren't available this is NE)

Value	Definition
MC	Minimal Concern
MN	Minor
MO	Moderate
MR	Major
MV	Massive
DD	Data Deficient
NA	No Alien Population
NE	Not Evaluated

impactSEICATConfidence

Description: The confidence with which the variable impactSEICAT was scored for a given taxon. Guidance regarding the use of the confidence rating is taken from Hawkins et al. (2015) as modified therein from the EPPO pest risk assessment decision support scheme (Alan MacLeod 09/03/2011; revised 28/04/2011; copied from CAPRA, version 2.74; 2).

Type: Factor with 3 levels (and NA)

Value	Definition
high	Approximately 90% chance of assessment being correct. There is direct relevant observational evidence to support the assessment; and impacts are recorded at the typical spatial scale over which original native communities can be characterised; and there are reliable/good quality data sources on impacts of the taxa; and the interpretation of data/information is straightforward; and data/information are not controversial or contradictory.
medium	There is some direct observational evidence to support the assessment, but some information is inferred; and/or impacts are recorded at a spatial scale which may not be relevant to the scale over which original native communities can be characterized, but extrapolation or downscaling of the data to relevant scales is considered reliable, or to embrace little uncertainty; and/or the interpretation of the data is to some extent ambiguous or contradictory.
low	There is no direct observational evidence to support the assessment, e.g., only inferred data have been used as supporting evidence; and/or impacts are recorded at a spatial scale which is unlikely to be relevant to the scale over which original native communities can be characterized, and extrapolation or downscaling of the data to relevant scales is considered unreliable or to embrace significant uncertainties; and/or evidence is poor and difficult to interpret, e.g., because it is strongly ambiguous; and/or the information sources are considered to be of low quality or contain information that is unreliable.

impactSEICATSource

Description: The reference or sources that were used to score impactSEICAT for a given taxon. The reference should be to the impact assessment conducted rather than to all the primary sources.

Type: character or NA

Values: reference(s)

impactExpertOpinion

Question addressed: How do experts rank the negative impacts of alien taxon in the Prince Edward Islands in 2015?

Description: This was used for the first report, but is deprecated in future reports as it is not transparent (Zengeya et al., 2017)

Type: Factor with 7 levels (and NA)

Value	Definition
-------	------------

Severe	~Massive
Major	~Major
Some	~Moderate
Few	~Minor
Negligible	Minimal Concern
DD	Data Deficient
NE	Not Evaluated

RiskAnalysis

Question addressed: Has a risk analysis of the alien taxon been completed for the Prince Edward Islands?

Description: Whether a risk analysis has been completed for the species according to the Risk Analysis for Alien Taxa (RAAT) framework (Kumschick et al. 2020), approved by the Alien Species Risk Analysis Review Panel, and submitted to DFFE

Relevant indicator(s): 4.1, 4.3, 4.5, 4.8

Type: Factor with 2 levels

Values: TRUE or FALSE

RiskAnalysisSource

Description: The reference that was used to score RiskAnalysis

Type: character or NA

Values: reference(s), ideally to a document with a doi

RiskAssessmentCompleted

Description: Whether a 'risk assessment' (in some cases technically a risk analysis) has been submitted to DFFE on the taxon, this might be support of an import application and so would need to include information specified in the NEM:BA A&IS Regulations, however, there is not set framework for such documents. In the case of import application, the 'risk assessment' (technically a risk analysis) might have been reviewed by SANBI and maybe also ASRARP. It is a requirement of the status report to report on species for which a 'risk assessment' has been completed.

Type: Factor with 2 levels

Values: TRUE or FALSE

speciesTreated

Question addressed: Has the taxon been subject to control efforts in the Prince Edward Islands between 1 January 2020 and 31 December 2022?

Description: If there are records of management having been implemented.

Relevant indicator(s): 4.5

Type: Factor with three levels

Value	Definition
NE	There has not been an evaluation of whether management has been implemented.
no	No populations were managed.
yes	One or more populations have had some management.

speciesTreatedConfidence

Description: The confidence with which the variable speciesTreated was scored for a given taxon

Type: Factor with 3 levels (and NA)

Value	Definition
high	There are readily available, up-to-date, records that management has (or has not) been applied to the species within the reporting period, and similarly that biocontrol agents have (or have not) established and are still present.
medium	Records of management (or a lack of management) are cited in other reports but were not available to be scrutinised. In the case of biocontrol agents, the level of confidence would depend on the level of evidence that the agents had established in the field.
low	There are indications that previous recorded attempts to control the species prior to the reporting period (i.e., >3 years ago) have continued or were discontinued, but no details are available beyond personal communications.

speciesTreatedSource

Description: The reference or sources that were used to score speciesTreated for a given taxon

Type: character or NA

Values: reference(s)

speciesTreatedEffect

Question addressed: If the taxon has been subject to control efforts in the Prince Edward Islands during the time period, how effective have these control efforts been relative to a situation where there was no control?

Description: outcome indicator for management based in part on that developed for assessing the efficacy of classical biological control programmes (Klein, 2011), and specifically the extent to which management is needed to maintain populations below a set threshold.

Relevant indicator(s): 4.8

Type: Factor with seven levels

Value	Definition
NA	The taxon has not been subjected to treatment, or whether it has been subjected to treatment is not known, i.e. speciesTreated is NE or none.
NE	There has been some treatment, but the effectiveness of such has not been evaluated or is otherwise not known.
counter-productive	There is evidence that control has led to further spread; has caused increases in abundance; and/or has made subsequent treatments more difficult without reducing the invasion.
ineffective	The extent of the invasion or the abundance of the species has continued to increase at rates that would have been expected if no control had been applied.
partial	Rate of increase in extent or abundance has slowed.
effective	Extent or abundance is decreasing or has ended up below a management threshold, but management is still required to maintain the populations below the threshold.
permanent	There is no more active management and despite this the population remains below the management threshold.
eradicated	The taxon has been successfully eradicated from The Prince Edward Islands.

speciesTreatedEffectConfidence

Description: The confidence with which the variable speciesTreatedEffect was scored for a given taxon

Type: Factor with 3 levels (and NA)

Value	Definition
high	There has been a published peer-reviewed quantitative assessment of the degree of control achieved.
medium	There is a report that is based on monitoring data.

Value	Definition
low	Expert opinion.

speciesTreatedEffectSource

Description: The reference or sources that were used to score speciesTreatedEffect for a given taxon

Type: character or NA

Values: reference(s)

realm

Question addressed: Which 'realm' is the species adapted to?

Description: This column is to enable cross-compatibility with South Africa's National Biodiversity Assessment process, and the allowed values are taken from here. This is a species level property and not a property of the invasion itself. To work out which taxa are invasive in a given realm, need to link to degreeOfEstablishment or introductionStatus. This is not taken directly from RegulatoryGrouping, in part as the values do not align (e.g., RegulatoryGrouping has freshwater, realm has InIndAqu)

Note that 'coastal' is not a realm, but a zone in which the marine, estuarine and terrestrial realms meet, and therefore coastal taxa will be marine and / or terrestrial and / or estuarine depending on the taxa preferences.

Type: A factor with 4 levels and any combination of these levels (and NA if it has not been classified). Multiple levels that apply are separated by a pipe delimiter.

Value	Definition
Estuarine	Inhabits estuarine systems.
InIndAqu	Inhabits inland aquatic systems (including freshwater lentic and lotic).
M	Inhabits marine ecosystems, including both pelagic and benthic.
T	Inhabits terrestrial ecosystems, note no separation is made for edaphic or aerial taxa.

realmSource

Description: The reference or sources that were used to score the realm for a given taxon

Type: character or NA

Values: reference(s), in this case it is acceptable to reference the NBA and the references contained therein.

notes

Description: And additional flags to add

Type: character or NA

historyOfInvasion

Description: Narrative of introduction date, maximum degree of establishment attained, control, and current status.

Type: character or NA if unknown

Differences with continental South Africa species list

Additional columns compared to mainland species list:

historyOfInvasion

Modified columns compared to mainland species list:

'RangeQDGC' for the mainland becomes 'RangeHMC' for the Prince Edward Islands as per le Roux et al. (2013).

Deleted columns compared to mainland species:

legallyImported

'legallyImported' column in the mainland species list is not applicable to the Prince Edward Islands. No living taxa can be introduced currently into Marion Island under any circumstances.

PermitsGranted

Column in mainland species list. Rationale: permits are granted only for the mainland nowadays; no aliens are allowed on the islands. Therefore, this column does not have a purpose for PEIs.

PermitsRefused

Similar rationale to PermitsGranted for PermitsRefused column.